

Consistent Group Constants for the Buckled Hyperfine SP_3 Equations

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ABSTRACT

The traditional method for deriving the multigroup SP_3 equations from the Linear Boltzmann Neutron Transport Equation (NTE) first discretizes the energy variable into a group structure, and then discretizes the angular variable. In this paper, we flip the order of discretization, where the SP_3 approximation is applied in continuous energy, and then the multigroup approximation is applied. We use a homogeneous mixture of fuel and moderator with imposed spatial buckling B^2 and solve the slowing-down spectrum on a hyperfine grid. The solution is compared to the conventional infinite-medium slowing-down solution, and the updated slowing-down spectrum is used to calculate the effect of streaming on anisotropy on few-group cross-sections and diffusion coefficients. A parametric study over leakage shows that the greatest difference in scalar flux from the traditional solution is in the fast regions. The results also show that while the difference between the flux spectra are small, the reformulation has a meaningful impact on the few-group cross-sections and diffusion coefficients.

Keywords: SP_3 , Hyperfine Slowing-Down, High-Performance Computing

1. INTRODUCTION

The conventional multigroup neutron transport equation (NTE) is obtained by first discretizing the energy dependence into G energy groups (multigroup approximation), and then performing some angular discretization, typically using spherical harmonic functions on the scattering source. Simplified Spherical Harmonics (SP_N) theory is an angular approximation that casts the linearized Boltzmann equation as an enhanced diffusion theory that is justified using either asymptotic or variational analyses in the scattering dominant regime. The computational advantage of the SP_N equations is the linear system contains $(N + 1) \cdot G$ unknowns compared to $(N + 1)^2 \cdot G$ for the conventional P_N equations.

In this work, the order of discretizations is switched from "group to angle" to "angle to group". The resulting equations are SP_N equations having a similar form as the traditional ones, but the weighting spectra to compute group constants are different. The goal of this work is to quantify this difference for homogeneous mixture 1-D, anisotropic (SP_3) transport problems with imposed geometric buckling B^2 , and propose a operator-driven numerical technique to solve for scalar flux on a hyperfine logarithmically-spaced group structure.

We use an infinite homogeneous mixture of ^{238}U and ^1H with known number densities, total, scattering, and fission cross-sections from ENDF/B-VIII.0 with an imposed buckling B^2 . We then solve for the hyperfine group-to-group (gtg) scattering cross-section moments with the goal of collapsing these cross-sections down to a few group structure weighted by a more accurate flux spectrum [1]. Results are shown for the norms of the leakage dependent slowing-down spectra, and percentage difference of the 8-group cross-sections and diffusion coefficients using the new weighting spectra versus the traditional ones.

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2. THEORY

The traditional method for performing this slowing-down calculation is called the scattering source method, detailed in [2]. The downscattering range is bounded on the interval $\alpha E' \leq E \leq E'$ or $u' \leq u \leq u + \ln(1/\alpha)$, where α is the scattering parameter, $\alpha = (\frac{A-1}{A+1})^2$, and $0 \leq \alpha < 1$. The energy is bounded from $E_{max} = 10$ MeV to $E_{min} = .01$ eV. This calculation does not account for any upscattering—as such there is an unphysical decrease at low energies, but this does not impact the fast-spectrum results where the differences in the group constants are significant. Future work will implement thermal upscattering within this framework, although we do not expect much difference from the conventional approach.

2.1. Continuous-Energy Buckled SP₃ Equations

We derive the continuous energy SP₃ equations using an elimination scheme based on solid harmonics proposed by Davison [3]. An in-depth derivation of the multigroup case is shown in an article by Chao [4]. To our knowledge, this approach had not previously been applied to continuous energy. More details on our continuous-energy SP_N derivation will be provided in a full journal article, but the general idea is laid out here. First, the continuous-lethargy P_n equations are written for $n = 0$ to 3 using the recursion relation. In the solid harmonic process, the solid-harmonic angular flux is defined as

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{U}, E) = \frac{U^n}{2n+1} \sum_{m=-n}^n Y_n^m(\hat{\Omega}) \psi_n^m(\mathbf{x}, u), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the position vector, $\hat{\Omega}$ is the direction variable, E is energy, Y_n^m is the spherical harmonic function, and ψ_n^m is the corresponding moment. The 2-D angular or direction variable $\hat{\Omega}$ defined on the surface of the unit sphere is augmented with a radial coordinate U to make a 3-D solid harmonic variable, \mathbf{U} .

A recursion relation is obtained in the solid harmonics form, and the corresponding SP₃ equations are

$$\nabla_U \cdot \nabla \Psi_1 = \Sigma_t \Psi_0 + \mathcal{S}_0 \Psi_0 + Q_0, \quad (2a)$$

$$\nabla_U \cdot \nabla \Psi_2 = -3\Sigma_t \Psi_1 - \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \Psi_0 + 3\mathcal{S}_1 \Psi_1, \quad (2b)$$

$$\nabla_U \cdot \nabla \Psi_3 = -5\Sigma_t \Psi_2 - 3\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \Psi_1 + U^2 \nabla_U \cdot \nabla \Psi_1 + 5\mathcal{S}_2 \Psi_2, \quad (2c)$$

$$0 = -7\Sigma_t \Psi_3 - 5\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \Psi_2 + U^2 \nabla_U \cdot \nabla \Psi_2 + 7\mathcal{S}_3 \Psi_3. \quad (2d)$$

Here ∇_U is a gradient operator that acts on the solid harmonic variables, Σ_t is the total cross-sections, and Q_0 is the isotropic fission source. \mathcal{S}_n is the scattering operator

$$\mathcal{S}_n = \int_0^\infty dE' \Sigma_{sn}(E' \rightarrow E), \quad (3)$$

where $\Sigma_{sn}(E' \rightarrow E)$ is the n -th Legendre moment of the double-differential scattering cross section for energy transfer E' to E . The SP₃ transport equation can be written in operator notation by defining the net loss operator

$$\mathcal{L}_n = (2n+1)(\Sigma_t - \mathcal{S}_n). \quad (4)$$

Given this notation, the solid harmonic elimination process is used to obtain the continuous-energy SP₃ equations:

$$\begin{aligned} 9\nabla^4 \phi_0 + (\mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 + (9\mathcal{L}_1 + 4\mathcal{L}_3) \mathcal{L}_0) \nabla^2 \phi_0 + \mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 \mathcal{L}_1 \mathcal{L}_0 \phi_0(E) \\ = (\mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 \mathcal{L}_1 - (9\mathcal{L}_1 + \mathcal{L}_3) \nabla^2) Q(E) \end{aligned} \quad (5a)$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 \phi_2(E) = -\frac{9}{2} \nabla^2 \phi_0(E) + \frac{1}{2} (9\mathcal{L}_1 + 4\mathcal{L}_3) (\mathcal{L}_0 \phi_0 - Q_0(E)), \quad (5b)$$

where $\nabla^4 = \nabla^2 \nabla^2$.

The internal source is assumed to equal the fission source $Q(E) = \chi(E)$ and the buckling approximation is then applied to replace the spatial gradients with the buckling B^2 that accounts for leakage. These are

$$\begin{aligned} [9B^4 + B^2(\mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 + 9\mathcal{L}_1 + 4\mathcal{L}_3) \mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 \mathcal{L}_1 \mathcal{L}_0] \phi_0(E) \\ = (\mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 \mathcal{L}_1 + B^2(9\mathcal{L}_1 + \mathcal{L}_3)) \chi(E) \end{aligned} \quad (6a)$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}_3 \mathcal{L}_2 \phi_2(E) = -\frac{9}{2} B^2 \phi_0(E) + \frac{1}{2} (9\mathcal{L}_1 + 4\mathcal{L}_3) (\mathcal{L}_0 \phi_0 - \chi(E)). \quad (6b)$$

These equations contain two unknown functions of energy: ϕ_0 is the scalar flux spectrum and ϕ_2 is another spectrum that accounts for some of the anisotropy present in the transport solution.

2.2. Computation of Group Constants

Once the fluxes are known, the updated flux weighted cross-sections and diffusion coefficients in the multigroup SP₃ equations are calculated for each moment, where $\Phi_0 = \phi_0 + \phi_2$ and $\Phi_2 = \phi_2$. The updated cross-sections and diffusion coefficients are obtained from

$$\Sigma_{tg}^n = \frac{\int_g \Sigma_t(E) \Phi_n(E) dE}{\int_g \Phi_n(E) dE}, \quad (7a)$$

$$\Sigma_{sl, g' \rightarrow g}^n = \frac{\int_g \int_{g'} \Sigma_{s\ell}(E' \rightarrow E) \Phi_n(E') dE' dE}{\int_{g'} \Phi_n(E') dE'}, \quad (7b)$$

$$D_{g',g}^n = \frac{\int_g \mathcal{L}_{n+1, g'}^{-1} \Phi_n(E) dE}{\int_g \Phi_n(E) dE}, \quad (7c)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{n+1}^{-1} is the inverse of the $n+1$ moment of the loss operator. For the hyperfine calculation, the weighting spectrum ϕ is assumed to be constant over a small bin width. For the group condensation, the cross-sections are weighted by the calculated slowing-down spectrum. These updated group constants are used to solve the SP₃ equations. Swapping the order of discretization operations changes the weighting factors for computing the group constants.

3. COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

To begin this slowing-down calculation, a number of groups is chosen, and gtg cross-sections are generated. A geometric buckling B^2 is specified for the purpose of this paper—this would normally be obtained using a different calculation.

The SP₃ equations in Sec. 2 are written in terms of lethargy where the scattering operator in the slowing down (target at rest) range is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_n = \int_u \Sigma_n^{gtg}(u' \rightarrow u) du &= \int_u \int_{u'} p(u' \rightarrow u) \Sigma_{sn}(u') du' du \\ &= \frac{\Sigma_{s0}}{1-\alpha} \int_{u_{lower}}^{\min(u+\ln(1/\alpha), u_{upper})} \int_{u'_{lower}}^{\max(u'_{upper}, u+\ln(1/\alpha))} e^{u'-u} P_l(\mu) du' du, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the scattering cosine $\mu(u', u) = \frac{A+1}{2}e^{\frac{u'-u}{2}} - \frac{A-1}{2}e^{\frac{u-u'}{2}}$, is a known lethargy-dependent quantity.

The method integrates from the bin minimum to the bin maximum unless $u - \ln(\alpha)$ falls within a bin. The first integral in Eq. (8) is performed analytically [5]. However, the second integral must be evaluated numerically for Legendre polynomial orders $0 \rightarrow 3$. These S_n operators are lower triangular and dense when upscattering is neglected and ^1H is present. They are set up such that the exact scattering contribution between groups g' and g are stored in $G \times G$ matrix, where G is the number of logarithmically-bins bins from E_{max} to E_{min} .

Building these large operators are quite numerically intense. Solving for these cross-sections is performed in parallel using Numba's JIT (just-in-time) compiler. JIT compiles the native code with no *Python-C API* calls, and is Numpy compatible. This compiler supports automatic parallelization, optimizations and vectorization, and no interpreter overhead. JIT is limited by the user having very limited control over memory allocation.

Generating cross-sections requires two loops over incident and outgoing energy groups, plus an integration step. Using a quadrature rule is accurate, but computationally prohibitive to perform over each combination of g' and g on a hyperfine grid. For ^1H , there are prohibitively many groups to integrate in serial. Integrating in parallel with Numba's JIT compiler, the calculation for 25000 groups (Fig. 2a) can be generated in seconds rather than days, at the cost of increased memory usage.

To calculate the loss operators in Eq. (4), the total cross-section vector is diagonalized. Then, the loss operators \mathcal{L}_n are calculated for each Legendre moment. From here, the flux weighted total, fission, and scattering cross-sections are computed using the relationships in Eqs. (7), as well as the diffusion coefficients for 8 groups using traditional quadrature integration. Table I shows the energy ranges of the 8 group structure.

Table I. Energy Group Indexes and Boundaries.

Group	Energy Range (eV)
1	$1.0000 \times 10^7 - 7.4989 \times 10^5$
2	$7.4989 \times 10^5 - 5.6234 \times 10^4$
3	$5.6234 \times 10^4 - 4.2169 \times 10^3$
4	$4.2169 \times 10^3 - 3.1623 \times 10^2$
5	$3.1623 \times 10^2 - 2.3714 \times 10^1$
6	$2.3714 \times 10^1 - 1.7783 \times 10^0$
7	$1.7783 \times 10^0 - 1.334 \times 10^{-1}$
8	$1.334 \times 10^{-1} - 1.000 \times 10^{-2}$

4. RESULTS

The difference between the SP_3 the traditional method is computed using a L_2 norm on the flux moments, and a percentage difference on the cross-sections and diffusion coefficients. All percentage errors are between the ϕ_0 weighted cross-sections and the Φ_0 weighted cross-sections.

4.1. Comparison of Scattering Source to $B^2 = 0$ SP_3 Methods

In the SP_3 method, setting $B^2 = 0$, reduces the problem to a purely isotropic infinite medium problem, which should reduce to the method seen in [2]. When comparing the normalized fluxes between the two methods at $B^2 = 0$ (Fig. 1), we observe that the spectra are different. The scattering source method approximates the cumulative downscatter from a range of higher energy groups with some weighting

Figure 1. Comparison of normalized Scattering Source to SP₃ Method of solving for ϕ_0 with different number of groups. The magnitude of the percent difference on the y-axis decreases as the Δu decreases.

spectrum, where the approach shown in Sec. 3 (the SP₃ solver, where $B^2 = 0$) calculates the exact probability and contribution from a higher group g' to a lower group g , as shown in Eq. (3).

For ²³⁸U, accurately capturing the transition probability is extremely important due to resonance scattering, especially in the upper energies of the resolved resonances. If there are few groups available for downscattering, calculating the exact gtg cross-section becomes more important, and the ²³⁸U gtg cross-sections are only non-zero on a small range near the diagonal.

The scattering source method essentially smears the group contributions over the range of downscatter. The new method of forming the $G \times G$ matrix exactly calculates the contributions, with the only error arising from discretization. Neutron balance is conserved macroscopically for scattering source and microscopically for the method defined in Sec. 3 [1]. The new method has a stronger coupling, with less scattering kernel approximation, between each g', g pair.

This method increases the computational load (wall time and memory), but there is a trade off for more accurate infinite mixture slowing-down problems. This difference is compounded when a geometric buckling term $B^2 \neq 0$ is introduced. The scattering source method is a useful reference solution because its computationally inexpensive and scales linearly with the number of groups. Our goal here is to quantify the effect of B^2 and 3rd order anisotropy on ϕ_0 , ϕ_2 , and reconstruct the angle dependent cross-sections and diffusion coefficients.

The percent difference between the solutions decreases as the number of groups increases and the gtg resolution increases. This is expected, because as $\lim_{\Delta u \rightarrow 0}$ (continuous energy), we see the solutions converge onto one another, as the number of groups that a neutron interacting with ²³⁸U can downscatter into increases. This is shown in Fig. 1, where the maximum percent error between the traditional and SP₃ calculations decreases $5\times$ as the number of groups increases by $5\times$.

4.2. Code Profiling

Solving the slowing-down spectrum as a system of linear equations as described requires creating large $G \times G$ matrices that embed the gtg coupling. Building cross-section data scales favorably in time, as shown in Fig. 2a. However, once the \mathcal{S}_n operators are build, the \mathcal{L}_n operation must be performed. This operation scales G^2 , and solving the system directly using Numpy's linear algebra solver also scales G^3 in time. All calculations were performed on U-M's Great Lakes cluster using 3.0-GHz Intel Xeon Gold 6154 processors with 36 cores.

(a) Time scaling of the SP_3 solver.

(b) L_2 norm of reference and SP_3 spectra, $B^2 = 0$.

Figure 2. Comparison of time scaling and spectral accuracy for the SP_3 solver.

Figure 2b shows the norm on the scattering source and SP_3 solutions. As G increases, both methods approach the correct answer, but the SP_3 method accounts for transition probabilities more accurately.

4.3. 1-D Flux Weighted Few-Group Constants

Table II shows the values of the $n = 0$ diffusion coefficient moment $D_{g',g}^0$ from Eq. (7c) where the Table II reads g' from left to right and g from top to bottom.

Table II. Diffusion Coefficient Matrix, $B^2 = 0$, 20,000 Groups.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
0.45315	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.048154	0.28489	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.0033427	0.019279	0.14719	0	0	0	0	0
$4.5379e^{-4}$	0.0026177	0.020481	0.13045	0	0	0	0
$7.2601e^{-5}$	$4.1879e^{-4}$	0.0032771	0.021678	0.13188	0	0	0
$1.1995e^{-5}$	$6.9192e^{-5}$	$5.4144e^{-4}$	0.0035820	0.022326	0.13756	0	0
$2.2909e^{-6}$	$1.3215e^{-5}$	$1.0341e^{-4}$	$6.8412e^{-4}$	0.0042644	0.026954	0.14420	0
$3.5628e^{-7}$	$2.0551e^{-6}$	$1.6082e^{-5}$	$1.0639e^{-4}$	$6.6320e^{-4}$	0.0041923	0.023340	0.11758

A parametric study of leakage parameter B^2 was performed. B^2 values between -0.025 and 0.025 were tested, and the greatest difference in the scalar flux (as compared to the $B^2 = 0$) case came in the fission energy range. This is not surprising, as fission neutrons stream out of the system more easily than thermal neutrons. We do not see a large difference when imposing B^2 between a minimum and a maximum (Fig. 3a). Figure 3b shows that when compared to the $B^2 = 0$ case, there is a small percentage difference in the flux in the thermal neutron ranges. However, we see up to a 1% difference in the fluxes as $|B^2|$ increases, where positive B^2 has a stronger impact on ϕ_0 than negative B^2 . That change has an impact on the Φ_0 weighted gtg scattering cross-sections when compared to the $B^2 = 0$ case.

The updated $\Phi_0 = \phi_0 + 2\phi_2$ weighted cross-sections are calculated and compared to their ϕ_0 counterparts with $B^2 = [-0.001, -0.0005, 0.0, 0.0005, 0.001]$, shown in Table III and Table IV, where values are percent differences for Group 1 or the top left element in the matrix. B^2 was increased to highlight the difference from the infinite medium case. The L_2 norm between the ϕ_0 and Φ_0 is much larger when leakage is introduced, as seen in Fig. 4. We observe that the percent difference on the cross-sections and

 Figure 3. Flux moments ϕ_0 and ϕ_2 .

 Figure 4. $\|\phi_0 - \Phi_0\|$ as a function of B^2

diffusion coefficients increase when there is anisotropy and leakage, proving how important accurately capturing Φ_0 is. When comparing the Φ_0 weighted diffusion coefficient to the ϕ_0 weighted diffusion coefficient (Eqs. (7)), we see that the coefficients change more as B^2 increases.

 Table III. Uranium Percent Difference, 20,000 \rightarrow 8 Group Collapse, Fission Energy Range (Group 1)

B_2	Σ_t	Σ_{s0}^{gtg}	Σ_{s1}^{gtg}	Σ_{s2}^{gtg}	Σ_{s3}^{gtg}	Σ_f
-0.001	0.00816796	0.0762102	0.210772	0.0829296	0.163904	0.053632
-0.0005	0.00206575	0.0187727	0.0506127	0.0199845	0.0395177	0.0130767
0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.36×10^{-14}	9.73×10^{-13}	1.70×10^{-12}	0.00E+00
0.0005	0.00193281	0.0189547	0.056497	0.0219523	0.0434018	0.0140882
0.001	0.00788708	0.0764742	0.222399	0.0867902	0.171548	0.0555977

Table IV, which has the Hydrogen results, shows that as the Legendre order increases, the percent difference in the few-group cross-sections also increase. The updated g_tg cross-sections are more dependent on ϕ_2 for Hydrogen than for Uranium. We make no claim that our results are more accurate than current SP₃ solvers, but we do note that the values are different, showing that changing the order of SP₃ derivation from "energy then angle" to "angle to energy" produces different few-group coefficients.

Finally, Table V shows the percentage difference of the first element in the diffusion coefficient matrix for the mixture. Again, we see that as B^2 increases, the effect on the diffusion coefficient increases.

Table IV. Hydrogen Percent Difference, 20,000 \rightarrow 8 Group Collapse, Fission Energy Range (Group 1)

B_2	Σ_t	Σ_{s0}^{gtg}	Σ_{s1}^{gtg}	Σ_{s2}^{gtg}	Σ_{s3}^{gtg}
-0.001	0.0818901	0.125584	0.167399	0.258919	0.432381
-0.0005	0.0198134	0.0311471	0.0413319	0.0636106	0.10577
0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.49×10^{-14}
0.0005	0.0221114	0.0306301	0.0414298	0.0652004	0.110824
0.001	0.0863997	0.124384	0.167396	0.261826	0.442072

Table V. Percent Difference in the Diffusion Matrix, 20,000 \rightarrow 8 Group Collapse, Group 1 \rightarrow 1

B^2	D
-0.001	0.255871
-0.0005	0.0806761
0.0	0.0183425
0.0005	0.0657372
0.001	0.226028

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a numerical method for solving the continuous-energy SP₃ equations on a hyperfine lethargy grid with an imposed buckling B^2 , reversing the traditional order of multigroup and angular discretizations. Applying the SP₃ expansion prior to energy grouping modifies both the scalar flux ϕ_0 and the higher moment ϕ_2 , leading to altered few-group cross sections and diffusion coefficients. Parametric studies show that the largest spectral deviations occur in the fast-energy range and increase with leakage, indicating that anisotropy effects captured in ϕ_2 are important for accurate few-group data. The Numba-accelerated implementation enables the construction and solution of hyperfine SP₃ systems with imposed geometric buckling B^2 . Future work will incorporate thermal upscattering, and apply the collapsed constants to k -eigenvalue, pin cell, and diffusion benchmarks.

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